

On Refinery-Wide Control Loop Performance Assessment

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Abstract: Rainer Dittmar's career is rooted in industrial experience, working at PCK refinery and Honeywell and later as the professor of automation at the West Coast University of Applied Sciences, Germany. He was a visiting professor at the University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB), the University of Auckland, New Zealand, the University of Stellenbosch, South Africa and University of Ottawa, Canada.

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After working in industry for many years, I went back to university in 1996. Shortly after that, I heard Nina's name for the first time when I read her paper „Refinery-wide control loop performance assessment“. The paper stimulated me to start a similar project with Sasol and PCK Schwedt Refinery in Germany. End of the 90s, the first commercial CPM tools were available, and we decided to use an on-site version of Honeywell LoopScout. Together with some of my students who installed the software and did the first examinations under real industrial conditions, and with engineers from Sasol and PCK, the project was a success and valuable experience could be gained. It was Nina's paper, which gave us useful hints for project execution and for the selection of „tuning parameters“ for the CPM software.

Since then, I regularly read Nina's contributions on conferences and in journals, in particular with respect to control performance monitoring, and disturbance detection and analysis. I was always impressed how she selected relevant industrial problems, and connected theoretical soundness of the methods presented with aspects of practical applicability in the process industries.

Unfortunately, we do not know each other face-to-face. Nevertheless, I wish to thank you for the inspiration you gave to my work. My best wishes on the occasion of your retirement, and good luck and health for many years to come.

REFERENCES

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